

THE LANGUAGE AND STYLE OF MASS MEDIA.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10684628>

Abstract. *It is hard to imagine any area of modern society experiencing the process of globalization without the language of the media. The breadth of media opportunities requires an in-depth study of their activities and development, and their impact on the audience. Media science is a new interdisciplinary field based on traditional methods. The formation of the language of the media is closely linked to their common mission. How viewers perceive information also depends on what tool is used to convey it. Each media uses its own language and methods of updating information to shape its essence, which in turn influences perceptions of existence.*

Key words: *Newspaper items, mass communication, journalism, essential elements.*

ЯЗЫК И СТИЛЬ СРЕДСТВ МАССОВОЙ ИНФОРМАЦИИ.

Аннотация. *Трудно представить какую-либо сферу современного общества, переживающую процесс глобализации, без языка средств массовой информации. Широта возможностей СМИ требует глубокого изучения их деятельности и развития, их воздействия на аудиторию. Медиаведение — новая междисциплинарная область, основанная на традиционных методах. Формирование языка СМИ тесно связано с их общей миссией. То, как зрители воспринимают информацию, также зависит от того, какой инструмент используется для ее передачи. Каждое СМИ использует свой язык и методы обновления информации для формирования ее сути, что, в свою очередь, влияет на восприятие существования.*

Ключевые слова: *Газетные материалы, массовая коммуникация, журналистика, реквизиты.*

Introduction. Today, the community has a great and fast opportunity to get the latest news through countless media outlets. No matter how information is received, it is expressed through language.

Journalism is a creative profession. The journalist must be clear and concise. He is asked to use his thoughts and words in their proper place.

The status of media language depends on two factors: how we understand the term language and how media language ranks among the functional types of national language.

At present, the language of mass media is the dominant of all functional types of the national language, which includes the resources of all functional styles. In other words, the language of the media today, whether we like it or not, is a composite image of the national language.

Today, the media is recognized as the most effective and acceptable form of speech, an effective mechanism for shaping public opinion and mood.

It is hard to imagine any area of modern society experiencing the process of globalization without the language of the media. Extensive technical capabilities in the media help to express the information provided by the social sphere not only linguistically, but also non-linguistically. As a result, it is also described as the language of science, journalism and culture.

The mass media are mainly used for the following purposes of mass communication:

- 1) informing the audience about what is happening;
- 2) assessment and analysis of events, forecasting their further development;
- 3) assistance in social relations;
- 4) advertising;
- 5) education;
- 6) organization of entertainment events.

The breadth of media opportunities requires an in-depth study of their activities and development, and their impact on the audience. Media science is a new interdisciplinary field based on traditional methods.

Mass media is a common name for the means of conveying information to the general public - periodicals, radio, television and others.

The formation of the language of the media is closely linked to their common mission. Researchers divide these tasks into the following groups:

- information transmission;
- comment (often the statement of facts is accompanied by their interpretation, analysis and evaluation);
- introduction, teaching and spiritual education (the media serves to replenish the knowledge base of its audience through the transmission of cultural, historical, scientific information);
- the task of influence (the media is not called the fourth power in vain: its influence on public opinion is very strong, which is especially evident in major socio-political processes, including presidential elections);
- the function of entertainment (which means that the media is effectively received by the audience, generates great interest and satisfaction, gives aesthetic pleasure);
- hedonistic feature (this is not just about entertaining information. If any information in the process of transmission evokes a sense of satisfaction and meets the aesthetic needs of the recipient, it is received with great positive effect).

How viewers perceive information also depends on what tool is used to convey it. Each media uses its own language and methods of updating information to shape its essence, which in turn influences perceptions of existence.

Main body. In the process of transmitting and receiving information, interpersonal communication takes place. Communication is, first and foremost, a communicative phenomenon. It is a relationship between one or more individuals that involves mutual understanding and the transfer of information from one person to another or to more than one person.

Mass media:

- 1) psychological features of information reception;
- 2) information features;
- 3) values based on the goals set in the process of mass communication activities;
- 4) theoretical notions of language and text as a means of updating information.

In the process of conveying information in the media, the process of increasing the knowledge of the audience, in a sense, takes place. So what is the mediating role of language in this process of learning?

Language is an important means of communication and expression, and serves as a tool for human beings to systematically and actively understand the world and turn it into an experience. As a result, it is possible to see the world through information and language.

So how is the concept of “media language” interpreted today?

It is used in three different senses:

- First, the language of the media is a set of all types of texts created and distributed by the media;

- Secondly, it is an internal system of stable language. It has its own linguistic and methodological features and characteristics;

- Third, a separate system of mixed characters, consisting of a balance of oral and audiovisual parts for each media.

From the point of view of describing the language of the media, such an interpretation of this concept is consistent with the idea that “language is universal, systematic and intelligible”. Accordingly, language is primarily defined as the manifestation of any type of character system or similar system. Other sign systems, such as the language of music, the language of fiction, and the language of the media, have also been identified.

The method and forms of their materialization play an important role in the expression of information through language. conditions of human life should lead to the solution of the tasks associated with the cultural and historical tasks assigned to man. Not because people conveyed the meaning of objects to their interlocutors, or even because they were hesitant to clearly and completely recreate a similar concept, but because they co-operated with each other in a chain of emotional imaginations and one of the first manifestations of an inner concept; they understand, because in everyone's mind there is a corresponding but not exactly similar meaning. Linguistic communication, that is, the exchange of information, always requires the creation of specific linguistic forms based on certain models (texts). They, in turn, are reflected in the minds of the participants-partners. The dynamics of communication between the two poles requires:

- 1) a norm that allows for a “similar understanding” of the language units being created, and
- 2) the need for freedom of choice in such a creative process.

In order to ensure the effectiveness of communication and the task of re-analyzing knowledge, they must play a heuristic (creative) role in the process of learning language signs. That is, the form of knowledge, as a form of meaning, interacts with another meaningful object and, according to its own laws, tends to go beyond the pre-existing features in the process of development and progress.

Today, the media is understood as a disseminator of knowledge. Mass media means not only technical means or channels of information, but also social organizations and people involved in the process of disseminating information. It should be noted that language is not always used in the media only for the exchange of information. Information can also be obtained through nonverbal means, images.

In addition, we believe that a journalist should have the following qualities: theoretical knowledge of the basics of journalism; knowledge; imagination; public speaking skills; language skills, speech culture.

Conclusion. The media, as an active channel of linguistic influence, also plays an important role in the application and dissemination of certain information methods.

The concept of "information style" is directly related to mass communication, which serves to express the specific tone of communication with the reader, listener, audience. Every media outlet - newspaper, magazine, radio and television - has such a feature. As you know, every media outlet communicates with its audience in a unique way. In doing so, he uses the expressive mediastilistic and rhetorical tools necessary for any communication (including textual communication).

The role of the media in the uninterrupted flow of language processes is invaluable. This is determined not only by the changes that have taken place as a result of the introduction of new information technologies, but also by the qualitative changes in the general linguistic culture.

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